

LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOUR AMONG HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract:

Leadership captures the essentials of being able and prepared to inspire others. Effective leadership is based upon ideas-both original and borrowed-that are effectively communicated to others in a way that engages them enough to act as the leader wants them to act. A leader inspires others to act while simultaneously directing the way that they act. They must be personable enough for others to follow their orders, and they must have the critical thinking skills to know the best way to use the resources at an organization's disposal.

Key Words: Leadership Behaviour, School Teachers

Need for the Study:

The modern society makes an extracting demand on educational institutions. In this highly complex world, the ever increasing horizon of human knowledge staggers to the tremendous increase and exploration in intellectual, human, instructional and structure. The task of educational administration in this context becomes extremely complex. The multiplicity of situations, of socio – economic, cultural and political framework and its bearing on educational policies and implementation demand analytical capabilities of high order so as to comprehend the phenomena and find solutions which are relevant to the grass root bearing on educational policies and implementation demand analysis capabilities of high order so as to comprehend the phenomena and find solutions with are relevant to the grass root realities of the problems and effectives. This requires relevant knowledge, suitable skills and appropriate values and attitudes on part of the educational administration. The new frameworks and policies are being materialized through heads. In this context to study about the educational administration becomes very important. One of the most important administration behaviour is leadership.

The teacher is the dynamic force of the educational system. Education without a teacher is just like a body without soul, skeleton, flesh and blood, a shadow without substance. "There is no greater need for the strong manly men and womanly women as heads for the young". As social engineers, the heads can socialize and humanize the young by their man – like qualities.

The need of teacher involvement in school administration and attitude towards teaching of school heads for self correction, self satisfaction, to guide the conduct and behaviours, to shape the personality, to set up the ideals for students, to improve the relations with human being, for the development of society, for the professional excellences, to improve professional environment and to follow the norms and principals of the profession. There are number of factors that influence teacher involvement in school administration and attitude towards teaching in schools. Increased duties and demand on time, low pay & disruptive students have a significant impact on teacher's attitude towards their jobs. In addition, lack of support from staff at all levels has an effect on teacher attitude towards teaching. A correlation study determined whether factors such as heads involvement in school administration and their attitude towards teaching are contributing factors in a teacher's decision to change campuses. So the investigator wants to study the leadership behaviour of the teacher. Hence the need for present study.

Operational Definitions:

- **Leadership Behaviour:** refers to process of social influence in which one person can enlist the aid and support of others in the accomplishment of a common task.
- **High School Teachers:** refer to a person who teaches the students of VI through X standard in higher secondary schools in Madurai district.

Variables of the Study:

The variables involved in the study are as follows:

Dependent Variable:

Leadership behaviour

Independent Variables:

- Gender : Male / Female
- Age : upto 40 / 41 and above
- Qualification : B.Ed. / M.Ed.
- Teaching experience : upto 10 years / 11 and above years
- Residence : Rural / Urban

- Religion : Hindu / Others
- Community : SC, ST / Others
- Family income : Adequate / Inadequate
- Family type : Joint / Nuclear
- Marital status : Married / Unmarried
- School locality : Rural / Urban
- School kind : Unisex / Mixed
- Subject teaching : Arts / Science
- Nature of employment : Permanent / Temporary

Objectives of the Study:

- To measure the level of Leadership behaviour among the high school teachers.
- To find out whether the select independent variables influence the leadership behaviour among the high school teachers.

Hypotheses of the Study:

The study has been designed to verify the following hypotheses:

- High school teachers have average level of leadership behaviour.
- Select independent variables exerts a significant influence on leadership behaviour among high school teachers.

Methodology-In-Brief:

Sample:

A stratified representative sample of 175 High school teachers who are handling the classes VI through X standard in Higher secondary schools in Madurai district constituted with due representation given to the variables, viz. Gender, Residence and Subject teaching.

Tool:

Leadership Behaviour Rating Scale developed by Sathiyagirirajan S (2010), was used for data collection.

Technique:

Survey was the technique employed.

Statistical Treatment:

- ‘t’ – test between the means of large independent samples.
- Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation ‘r’.

Leadership Behaviour among School Teachers:

The empirical average score of Leadership behaviour among school teachers involved in this study is found to be 58.89, while the theoretical average is 50 only. Thus the Leadership behaviour among school teachers is found to be above the average level. To put it differently, school teachers’ leadership behaviour is found more satisfactory.

Differential Studies on Leadership Behaviour:

Leadership Behaviour and Independent Variables:

The details of results of test of significant difference between the mean scores of Leadership behaviour in terms of Independent variables are given in table.

Table: Statistical Measures and Results of Test of Significance of Difference Between the Means of Leadership Behaviour: Independent Variables – Wise

Variable	Sub-variables	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ - value	Significance At 0.05 level
Gender	Male	65	63.953	10.525	0.897	Not Significant
	Female	110	62.654	7.269		
Age	Upto 40	59	59.508	7.909	4.237	Significant
	41 and above	116	64.982	8.402		
Qualification	B.Ed.	97	63.804	9.173	1.162	Not Significant
	M.Ed.	78	62.307	7.849		
Teaching Experience	Below 5 years	136	63.367	9.047	0.762	Not Significant
	5 and above	39	62.333	6.956		
Residence	Rural	117	62.2393	8.972	2.087	Significant
	Urban	58	64.9483	7.605		
Religion	Hindu	120	65.366	7.543	5.139	Significant
	Others	55	58.272	8.872		
Community	SC/ST	40	63.925	7.395	0.297	Not Significant
	Others	135	62.903	8.959		

Family income	Adequate	135	62.777	8.890	1.021	Not Significant
	Inadequate	40	63.975	7.315		
Family type	Joint	110	62.672	8.937	0.952	Not Significant
	Nuclear	65	63.923	8.053		
Marital status	Married	135	63.118	8.757	0.054	Not Significant
	Unmarried	40	63.200	8.231		
School locality	Rural	134	62.9851	8.7555	0.435	Not Significant
	Urban	41	63.6341	8.2333		
School kind	Unisex	137	63.284	8.838	0.459	Not Significant
	Mixed	38	62.605	7.855		
Subject teaching	Arts	119	62.831	9.088	0.729	Not Significant
	Science	56	63.785	7.555		
Nature of employment	Permanent	118	62.610	8.796	1.194	Not Significant
	Temporary	57	64.228	8.200		

Hypotheses Verification:

The study has been designed to verify the following hypotheses:

- High school teachers have average level of Leadership behaviour -Accepted
- Select Independent variables exerts a significant influence on Leadership behaviour among high school teachers.
- Out of fourteen variables involved in this study, only three variables influence the Leadership behaviour among high school teachers. Hence the Hypothesis is Minimally Accepted.

Conclusions:

The major conclusions emerged out of the present study are presented below.

- Leadership behaviour among the among high school teachers is found above average level.
- Leadership behaviour among the among high school teachers is found dependent upon
 - Age
 - Residence
 - Religion
- Leadership behaviour among the secondary and high school teachers is found independent upon
 - Gender
 - Qualification
 - Teaching experience
 - Community
 - Family income
 - Family type
 - Marital status
 - School locality
 - School kind
 - Subject teaching
 - Nature of employment
- Leadership behaviour among the high school teachers is found is better facilitated by
 - Those who are in age group 41 and above above 40 than who are in age group upto 40
 - Those who are residing in urban area than those who are residing in rural area
 - Those who belong to Hindu religion than others

Educational Implications:

The findings of the present study revealed that leadership behaviour is found higher among the teachers who came from urban area, who are in the age group of above 40 and those who belongs to Hindu religion than others. Teachers play a very crucial role in achieving the objectives and its related development of our nation. Students are the backbone of the educational process. Education is a process and acts also as an instrument to bring out the innate behaviour of the individual. The destiny of a nation lies in its classroom. The strength of our nation depends on the teacher's ability to rear well educated, responsible, well adjusted youth who will step forward when the adult generation passes on the retirement. The students of today are the youths of tomorrow and future citizens of the country, therefore it is the responsibility of teachers, society and government to see that they are physically, mentally, emotionally and educationally healthy. The needful steps taken at this period ensures a healthy democracy in the country.

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